

SciComm Note: *Sight*

SUMMARY

- Visual methods are used in a wide range of science-communication activities and adopting a variety of techniques.
- They promote creativity, literacy, and engagement, and often involve collaboration and participation, making visible that which can be seen as well as that which can be hidden.
- To work effectively and with impact, visual science communication should be high quality, accurate and draw on training or professional expertise.
- Visual methods can lead to a range of impacts that are cognitive, social, attitudinal and emotional and which, in the right setting, can meet the needs of underserved people.
- Despite good uptake in science communication, there is still an opportunity to learn more about the role and implications of Generative AI in visual science communication, as well as how to plan and produce high-quality science-communication visual approaches collaboratively and with impact.

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INTRODUCTION

This SciComm Note focuses on one of the five senses – sight – considering the role of visual methods and those experienced via ‘seeing’ in science communication. Designed for science-communication practitioners and researchers who are using visual methods for the first time, it explores: Which visual methods seem **well-established** and which are **emerging**? What are the **strengths** and **weaknesses** of these approaches? And what **impacts** can visual science communication techniques have?

From a content analysis of research (2019 to 2025) gaps in understanding of visual science-communication methods and areas where further awareness of practice and/or investigation are also highlighted. A set of key questions for science communicators planning to use a visual approach are provided. Selected examples are included, with further information on all of the research incorporated in the corresponding open-access database (DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.18172544).

SCIENCE-COMMUNICATION METHODS

A wide range of visual science-communication methods are found in the literature. These include use of **illustration, photography, film, animation, video abstracts, infographics, and data visualisations**, through to approaches that incorporate different types of medium, like **visual poetry, theatre, dance, collaborative art, or social-media images**.

Various scientific areas are communicated from work on science as a discipline, to projects and interventions in chemistry, ecology, medicine, microbiology, neuroscience, public health, physics and new technologies. Projects connecting visual communication with disciplines including environmental science, conservation and health, respectively, are particularly prominent, sometimes but not always connected to climate science.

STRENGTHS OF SCIENCE COMMUNICATION THROUGH SIGHT

The research examined identifies many potential strengths in using visual science–communication methods. There are perceived benefits in terms of **creativity**, with visual methods being useful to support innovative approaches^[1]. Several examples involve cross–disciplinary contexts, where the potential to imaginatively connect concepts across fields has been an incentive to develop an image–based science–communication approach.

Visual approaches have strengths in relation to **literacy**, where using communication mechanisms that are reliant on sight alone avoids the need for literacy via language^[2]. Literacy is enhanced in terms of speed, where digesting information via an illustration for example, can provide a short cut to convey information.

In other examples, visual methods are used because they offer a simple way through which people can participate in research, for example by uploading photographs in a citizen science project. More novel strengths include the role of sight in text–based communication, including how we visualise spaces, punctuation and lettering, in order to make sense of content.

Visual messages have potential to reach a breadth of people almost instantly and strengths in terms of their **participatory** potential are often highlighted^[3]. Visualisations can be attractive, beyond those with an existing interest in science, technology engineering and mathematics (STEM), and have wide–ranging appeal to public audiences and participants.

The collaborative potential of some visual methods, for instance when working with illustrators, means they are identified as useful for inclusion, social justice or co–creation–based initiatives, with specific areas like the arts having a long history of tackling complex social issues. Visual science communication often takes place beyond traditional science–communication venues, like university campuses or museums, again suggesting potential for a broadening of audience reach.

Incorporating visual content enhances visibility, and memorability, and the perceived **impact** of communications^[4]. In some examples this involves

METHODS AND DATA

This SciComm Note is based on a co–creation workshop, content analysis and synthesis of research published and shared via Scopus, Science Direct and Pubmed between 1st January 2019 to 1st January 2025. Keyword searches (Title only) were performed for the following terms:

Visual OR graphic OR infographic OR animate/ion OR art OR sight OR illustrate/ion AND science communication OR public engagement OR citizen science

Conference papers, abstracts, editorials and grey literature were excluded. Thirty–six items were included in the analysis. The database, which includes full details of the materials and how each item was analysed, can be accessed here: doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18172544.

[1] Bevan, B., et al. (2021) The Main Course Was Mealworms: The Epistemics of Art and Science in Public Engagement. *Leonardo*, 54 (4): 456–461 https://doi.org/10.1162/leon_a_01835

[2] Blackburn, R.A.R. (2019) Using Infographic Creation as Tool for Science–Communication Assessment and a Means of Connecting Students to Their Departmental Research. *Journal of Chemical Education*. 96 (7): 1510–1514 <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jchemed.8b00981>

[3] Duckett, C.J., et al. (2021) Nights at the Museum: Integrated Arts and Microbiology Public Engagement Events Enhance Understanding of Science Whilst Increasing Community Diversity and Inclusion. 3 (5): 000231 <https://doi.org/10.1099/acmi.0.000231>

[4] Verma, A., et al. (2024) Visual Design as a Facilitator of Risk Observance Optimizing Message Reception and Memorability for Increased Public Engagement in *Routledge Handbook of Risk, Crisis, and Disaster Communication* <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003363330-11>

coupling a visual method with a relatively traditional, academic communication approach, such as the use of video abstracts alongside journal publications. In others, visuals provide the potential to heighten impact by forming a stronger narrative, value-based and/or emotional connection or the opportunity to utilise parallel communication approaches, like the use of social media.

Visualising that which can be **hidden** helps form connections with audiences and brings to the forefront unseen dimensions of an experience (for example, around health conditions) which may otherwise be unspoken or concealed^[5]. Visualisations can bring to life elements of science that could be naked to the human eye, for example how an airborne virus spreads or the intricacies of nanotechnology. Adding a graph, figure or chart to a text provides a visual support to understanding data that is presented, although accuracy is also vital.

WEAKNESSES OF SCIENCE COMMUNICATION THROUGH SIGHT

Despite their strengths much research acknowledges potential pitfalls in relation to the use of visual methods. This includes a perceived lack of understanding as to how the **quality** of visual content impacts on its reception, and concerns that images can be **misinterpreted**. Articles describes a fine line between making images attractive and **accurate**^[6]. There is a perceived lack of **training** and **knowledge** in relation to visual science-communication methods^[7], with the training that is provided under evaluated.

Developing visual science communication often involves working across disciplines. This can create **power** imbalances and confusion as to whether collaboration is the goal, or the output and/or outcomes of such relationships, and what this might imply about 'instrumentalising' some visual and artistic processes^[8]. Evaluations were critiqued for focusing most on the experiences of scientists or consequences in relation to STEM understanding or responsiveness.

Research also highlights a lack of appreciation and/or awareness of the skills of trained visual communication **professionals**, like graphic designers, and the value of their input^[9]. A lack of agreed **frameworks** or **guidance** for some visual science-communication methods can compound some weaknesses^[10], and some content is produced but poorly shared.

[5] Harrison, S.L., et al. (2023) Online Comic-based Art Workshops as an Innovative Patient and Public Involvement and Engagement Approach for People With Chronic Breathlessness. *Research Involvement and Engagement*. 9 (19):1-10 <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40900-023-00423-8>

[6] Lopez-Cantos, F. (2021) Scientific Image Forgery, Journalism, and Public Communication of Science. *International Journal of Sociotechnology and Knowledge Development*. 13 (3): 95-105 <https://doi.org/10.4018/IJSKD.2021070106>

[7] Zhang KE, & Jenkinson J. (2024) The Visual Science Communication Toolkit: Responding to the Need for Visual Science Communication Training in Undergraduate Life Sciences Education. *Education Sciences*, 14 (3): 296. <https://doi.org/10.3390/educsci14030296>

[8] Woodley, E., et al. (2024) Climate Stories: Enabling and Sustaining Arts Interventions in Climate Science Communication. *Geoscience Communication*, 5 (4): 339-354, <https://doi.org/10.5194/gc-5-339-2022>

[9] Monoyios, K., at al. (2024) Visuals as a Catalyst for Climate Science Communication, in *Storytelling to Accelerate Climate Solutions* https://doi.org/10.1007/978-3-031-54790-4_11

[10] Finkler, W. & Leon, B. (2019) The Power of Storytelling and Video: A Visual Rhetoric for Science Communication. *JCOM* 18 (05): A02 <https://doi.org/10.22323/2.18050202>

CO-CREATION

The development of this SciComm Note began with a workshop in July 2024, where exercises and discussion informed three research questions that then formed the basis for the research synthesis. Thank you to the participants in this workshop: Conan Lee, Dr Danijela Poljuha, Dr Gabriela Montorzi, Ian Cooke-Tapia, Dr Tullio Rossi and Valentin Gradisteanu, who gave their consent to be named, as well as the participants who prefer to remain anonymous. Thank you to Ana Vasconcelos who contributed to the analysis of materials for the SciComm Note during a sabbatical at the University of the West of England, Bristol.

IMPACTS

How are impacts different to strengths? Examples identify numerous positive impacts visual science-communication approaches have, gathered through research, evaluation or anecdote from projects, activities and/or experiences.

Visual methods are evidenced as impacting **intention, perception, cognition, enjoyment, understanding, engagement, behaviour, empowerment and recall** amongst visitors, audiences and participants, broadening the conversations and dialogues that could be held around scientific, health and environmental issues.

Adopting visual approaches allows participants to define their own **perspectives**, and make **connections** between concepts, in ways that may not be possible using other methods. Visualisations can tell **stories** and develop **narratives** in different ways and incorporate **emotional** and **empathetic** elements. Effective visual communication enhances the **efficiency** of messages, broadens **exposure** and increases their **memorability**.

Collaborative visual projects opened up opportunities for different kinds of 'output' that are less restrictive and more open than traditional formats of communication like academic publishing. For researchers and communicators, visual approaches enhance opportunities to develop **innovative** and **collaborative** skill sets, to recognise the potential input of collaboration, as well as the value of other disciplines, preferably in non-hierarchical ways.

Visual approaches provide a source of **enjoyment** and **creativity**, enhancing both **inspiration** and **reflection**, and can be used to enhance **transparency** around disciplines (e.g. capturing science and/or technologies in the making). Such methods can increase the **clarity, succinctness** and refinement of **explanation** around difficult concepts and enhance **uptake**, for example by policymakers, NGOs or via social media.

Working with different types of content creators and professionals, like artists and video producers, opens up science communication to different methods and different audiences. This sometimes means reaching **broader audiences**, though there are mixed results as to whether these audiences are more diverse. Evolving and accessible technologies provide further opportunities for innovative and impactful visualisations of scientific content and data, but there can be issues of trust to explore here (for example, around how accurate and/or manipulated images might be).

GAPS AND FURTHER RESEARCH

Areas requiring additional consideration included concerns about the increased use of Generative AI, where copyright regulations, privacy, accuracy and manipulation concerns were sometimes being outpaced by technologies creating visual content, requiring proactive measures amongst users to consider such issues. These were also important themes in the preceding co-creation workshop.

Even when using more traditional visual communication techniques, the ways in which visual content can enhance emotional connection raises questions about trust and manipulation. When inaccuracies are

introduced, it can be hard to 'retract' visual content. And whilst visual methods can extend the potential for participation to a broader groups, the assumption that they enhance engagement from under-represented people and communities in science communication was identified as needing greater evidence.

The skills to develop good, high-quality visual communication are underestimated according to some authors, and an area where there is a need for more training for science communicators. With increasing availability of programs that produce visual content, there are concerns not only about a surplus of low-quality visual content produced via cheaper tools but the detrimental impact this could have on those trained and working in visual-content production. Cumulatively this then creates missed opportunities to develop visual narratives and images that really resonate with people.

There is a need for better planning of visual content, enhanced quality of content and greater understanding of where and how visual communication might best meet the needs of audiences. As visual-content creators becoming more sophisticated in other fields of influence, it is becoming harder for visual science communicators to distinguish their content and stand out from the competition. Audiences can be volatile, with mediums that trade in image-based content, like social media, witnessing rapid changes in user preferences, and communicators at the mercy of algorithms over which they have limited control.

There is a desire for better understanding and evaluation of longitudinal impacts from visual science-communication approaches. This would enhance awareness of the role of visuals and have a knock-on effect on training and the quality of content that is produced. Evaluation of impact needs to go beyond superficial impacts to consider how relationships are developed through collaborations to be sustained and to understand the direct impacts visual approaches have on research when used with that intention (for instance, in citizen science). Evaluation of visual methods can focus on easy metrics, rather than deeper forms of engagement.

Visual approaches often require an 'open mind' and processes or people that can facilitate engagement between disciplines or different types of content creators. The need to consider accessibility for people with a visual disability when creating content was rarely explicitly addressed. This could be due to the examples analysed focusing on visual methods specifically or it may suggest it is an overlooked issue.

SELECTED READING AND RESOURCES

- Allen, W.L. (2018). Visual brokerage: Communicating data and research through visualisation. *Public Understanding of Science*, 27 (8), pp. 906–922. <https://doi.org/10.1177/0963662518756853>
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- Trumbo, J. (1999). Visual Literacy and Science Communication. *Science Communication*, 20 (4), pp. 409–425. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1075547099020004004>
- Ursyn, A. (2024) *The Transfer of Knowledge through Art and Visualization: Novel Technologies, Collaboration, and Visual Communication of Science-based Projects*. New York, U.S.A.: Routledge.

SCIENCE COMMUNICATION USING A VISUAL APPROACH: KEY QUESTIONS FOR PRACTITIONERS AND RESEARCHERS

1. Why will a visual approach enhance the goals of your communication approach?

- What are the potential benefits in terms of understanding, awareness, behaviour change, collaboration?
- Will it allow you to access new, different and/or underserved audiences/ participants?
- Can a visual method allow people to provide input to your activities in a different way?

2. Do you have the visual design skills for your planned communication approach?

- Is there training you can undertake?
- Should you be collaborating with a visual communication professional?
- Is it appropriate to use generative AI and/or a programme to generate your visual content?

3. What science communication method will you use?

- Which formats are most appropriate to the aims of your science communication approach?
- What strengths and limitations might they have for the goals of your communication?
- What method offers the best fit in terms of aspects like accuracy, narrative, creativity and/or co-creation?

4. Are there any ethical implications of using your visual communication method?

- Are there audiences or participants a visual communication method won't reach and is that significant?
- How will you consider any hierarchies of power or knowledge, if work is of a collaborative nature?
- Is there likelihood authenticity and/or accuracy of your content could be misconstrued and would this have implications?

5. Do you need to consider evaluation of your communication approach?

- Which groups will be relevant to include in evaluation of your communication (scientists, science communication practitioners, collaborators, audiences/ participants, other people)?
- Do you need to evaluate the impacts of your visual communication methods (e.g. on learning, awareness, creativity, research etc.)?
- Do you plan to evaluate the processes of your visual communication methods (e.g. as a collaboration, with participants, contributions to policy making etc.)?

Report

Database

These methods can be **creative**, help **simplify messages** and make **visible** what is otherwise unseen. They often involve **collaboration** and reach a wider range of **people**, which can broaden their potential **impact**.

Communicating using sight-based methods has multiple reported impacts including on **enjoyment**, **engagement** and **empowerment** for audiences, communicators, visual content producers and researchers.

There are many methods to communicate science through 'sight' from **illustration** to **photography**, **video abstracts** or **infographics**, to **art** and **images** shared on social media content.

Visual methods need to be **accurate** to avoid **misinterpretation**. They can require **professional** input and ideally, collaboration, between **science communicators** and **designers/artists**.

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